

LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECT OF THE CATEGORY OF SPACE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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INTRODUCTION

Some researchers suggest that communication is psychological process. People are not affected the same as one another by something because there are no people who are the same. So every person is individual. Inside of everyone there is "I". according to some facts, a well-known telephone company in New York thoroughly studied conversations via telephone in order to find out the most often used word in them. The result shows that the word is the subject pronoun "I". "I" was used 3990 times in 500 telephone conversations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Interaction between people is based on both verbal and nonverbal communication. A.Kasimov mentions that people are using

ABSTRACT

The article focuses on the comparison of distinctive features of nonverbal expressions, their similar and dissimilar peculiarities in English and Uzbek communication. The examples are provided in the English and Uzbek languages concerning culture specific nonverbal expressions. In this study we also mention some of the researchers' work, such as the contribution of Uzbek scholar to the study of nonverbal means in Uzbek communication.

around 35% verbal communication and 65% nonverbal communication in daily life. The peculiarities of nonverbal expressions and means in Uzbek communication were well-studied and researched by M.Saidkhonov.

According to M.Saidkhonov, there are three functions of nonverbal means used in Uzbek communication. They are the followings:

1. Nonverbal means used instead of verbal expressions.
2. Nonverbal means supplementing verbal expressions.
3. Nonverbal means used together with verbal expressions .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of nonverbal means used instead of verbal expressions serves to compensate for speech. For instance, "U norozi ma'noda

bosh chayqadi". "She gave a nod to express her disagreement".

Nonverbal means supplement verbal expressions. They are mainly used with a view to emphasizing stylistic meaning or expressiveness.

Men birinchi emasman! – dedi u jahl bilan. I am not the first – he said angrily.

Men birinchi emasman! – dedi u zavq bilan. I am not the first – he said excitedly.

If these two sentences are compared, we notice that the first expresses someone with an anger and a bad mood, whereas the latter expresses the person with the opposite character being delighted and happy.

As for the third function of nonverbal means in Uzbek, they can be used together with verbal expressions simultaneously in order to strengthen the meaning of verbal expressions in communication. The following example in English and Uzbek includes the use of both verbal and nonverbal expressions used together.

U noiloj o'z aybini tan olib, bosh irg'adi va "ha" deb qo'ydi.

She desperately admitted her fault nodding her head and said "yes".

As mentioned above, according to their functions, nonverbal means are used for several reasons as well as situations. They serve to compensate for verbal expressions and supplement them as well. Apart from that, they can even be used along with verbal expressions in parallel or simultaneous way.

In addition, nonverbal means in Uzbek communication were studied according to two aspects by S.Saidkhonov:

1. according to communicative and somatic features.
2. according to the use of nonverbal means.

People make use of various nonverbal expressions in everyday life regardless of their culture. There are also various commonly used nonverbal expressions in Uzbek culture, including nodding to approve and agree with something, shaking index finger to warn someone, clapping to praise somebody and also showing thumb up to mean something is great, perfect and worth.

In some regions local people try to greet with a huge and warm hug, consequently this can be considered the most acceptable way to show their respect. In cities all relatives kiss each other's cheek as much as they prefer. The Uzbek people apply nonverbal communication almost every day. For instance, women close to each other greet by kissing on the cheek or hugging. When they meet, they ask about their family and well-being. When men greet, they handshake and place their hand over their heart. If they are far away from each other, they may nod a little.

One of the similar features of Uzbek and English is the way of greeting between man and man who shake hands while greeting each other. However, generally asking loads of questions, such as about family, work, health during the greeting is typical of Uzbek people from the point of politeness and no detailed response for every question is accepted as a normal case that does not occur in the same way as English greeting. In addition, according to Uzbek culture, women greeting women, the older ones may grip an arm of each other. Friends and family members exchange kisses on the cheek and hugs each other. In England, the first meeting between women are generally done by shaking hands.

In Uzbekistan, greeting between man and woman may involve only saying "Assalomu

alaykum”, sometimes exchanging a nod. One of the distinguishing feature of Uzbek people is that there is no touch by people of the opposite gender, while it is normal by family members. As Uzbekistan is a Muslim country, both men and women do not touch with one another. Therefore, most men and women do not prefer a handshake. Nevertheless, a handshake is a form of greeting between men and women in England. Also, it is women who tend to extend their hand first.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, nonverbal expressions are not only gestures, but it is also concerned

with eye contact, touch, personal space and many more. Their use in Uzbek communication is not expressed totally in the same way as English. Undoubtedly, it is because they are culture specific and vary across cultures. The above-mentioned examples help us summarize that some of the nonverbal expressions in Uzbek convey similar meaning in English, while the others refer absolutely different things. So it is worth bearing in mind the possibility of some barriers in nonverbal communication between English and Uzbek.

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